

ISic1271

I.Sicily inscription 1271

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific (?)

Material

mosaic (?)

Object

pavement

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140760

1. Κλωδιανός
2. κὲ Μοῦσα
3. σὺν πεδίοις
4. ὑπὲρ εὐχῆς
5. ἐπέθηκαν.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492878

EDCS 39101640

PHI 140760

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0446 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Ferrua, A 1989. *Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.*

Vatican. At no.485

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